

Studies on Some New Phenothiazines: Ultraviolet and Infrared Spectral Characteristics of New Phenothiazines

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Manuscript received 28 June 1975, revised 12 August 1975, accepted 12 August 1975

Some new 10-N-acylamino phenothiazines have been prepared and their ultraviolet and infrared spectra have been discussed. An attempt has been made to show the N-acyl substitution effects on the course of absorption pattern of phenothiazines. It was interesting to find that N-acyl substitution showed bathochromic shift in the U.V. spectra of these compounds and carbonyl peaks in the I.R. spectra have been shifted to higher region by 20-35 cm^{-1} .

THE drug action of phenothiazine derivatives has generated interest in the synthesis and physico-chemical studies of new phenothiazines. In search of some specific antiulcer agents a few 10-N-acyl amino phenothiazines have been prepared, namely, 2-methoxy-10-(ter. butyl-amino)-acetyl (A), 2-methoxy-10- α -(ter. butyl amino)-propionyl (B), 2-methoxy-10- β -(ter. butyl amino)-propionyl (C), 2-chloro-10- α -(4'-methyl piperazinyl-1)-acetyl (D), 2-methoxy-10- α -(4'-methyl piperazinyl-1)-acetyl (E), 2-methoxy-10-

Compd. No.	% Elemental analysis						X	R	Z
	C		H		N				
	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found			
A	60.23	59.98	6.11	6.09	7.30	7.12	OCH ₃	CH ₂	NHC(CH ₃) ₃
B	61.14	61.30	6.14	6.14	7.13	7.39	OCH ₃	CH(CH ₃)	NHC(CH ₃) ₃
C	61.14	61.24	6.14	6.30	7.13	7.25	OCH ₃	CH ₂ CH ₂	NHC(CH ₃) ₃
D	51.07	50.86	4.96	4.88	9.40	9.08	Cl	CH ₂	
E	54.23	53.96	5.69	5.49	9.49	9.25	OCH ₃	CH ₂	
F	55.27	55.38	5.96	5.76	9.20	9.31	OCH ₃	CH ₂ CH ₂	
G	55.27	55.42	5.96	5.80	9.20	9.35	OCH ₃	CH(CH ₃)	
H	54.32	54.45	6.01	6.30	8.64	8.78	OCH ₃	CH ₂ CH ₂	
I	54.32	54.45	6.01	6.24	8.64	8.82	OCH ₃	CH(CH ₃)	

A-C as monohydrochlorides and D-I as dihydrochlorides.

β -(4'-methyl piperazinyl-1)-propionyl (F), 2-methoxy-10- α -(4'-methyl piperazinyl-1)-propionyl (G), 2-methoxy-10- β -(4'- β '-hydroxy-ethyl)-piperazinyl-1)-propionyl (H) and 2-methoxy-10- α -(4'- β '-hydroxy-ethyl)-piperazinyl-1)-propionyl (I) phenothiazine have been prepared by treating 2-substituted phenothiazines with respective haloacyl chloride¹. In the present paper U.V. and I.R. spectral characteristics of these phenothiazines are described.

Although enormous amount of work done on the absorption characteristic of sulphur bearing compounds¹ has been reviewed², there appear to be no systematic study on the phenothiazines, particularly on 10-N-acylamino derivatives. Besides investigating the antiulcer activity of these compounds it is interesting to study the N-acyl substitution effects on the course of absorption pattern of phenothiazines.

Experimental

Reagents : The phenothiazine derivatives were prepared in our laboratories as reported¹ and purified by column chromatography supplemented with T.L.C. Other reagents used for spectral analysis were of spectral grade (B.D.H.).

Spectrophotometers : The infrared spectra were recorded with a Perkin-Elmer model 137 spectrophotometer. The phenothiazines studied were prepared as KBr discs.

The ultraviolet spectra were recorded using model H 700-308 Hilger spectrophotometer. The cells were of 1 cm light path.

Results and Discussions

Ultraviolet spectra : Few references dealing with U.V. spectral data of substituted phenothiazines are available³⁻⁵. The U.V. spectra of compounds under study showed characteristic absorption both in intensity and in wave length and the values are listed in Table I. The most intense peak in the ethanolic solution was observed in the region of 232 to 236 nm, another peak was observed in the region of 250-260 nm. A flat region was also observed around 312 nm. However, if distilled water was taken as solvent, the broad band around 315 nm has disappeared. It may be due to the polar effects of the solvent which tend to shift down the absorption. The effect of N-substitution of phenothiazines on their U.V. spectrum can be clearly seen from the results observed (Table I). Phenothiazine itself exhibits two strong peaks at 253 nm and 320 nm³, 2-chlorophenothiazine exhibits at 256 and 320 nm⁶ and 2-methoxyphenothiazine also exhibit two peaks at 250 and 320 nm showing thereby that ring substitution at position 2 has little effect in their U.V. spectra. A shift of peak in 250 nm region towards longer wavelength is observed in the spectra of compounds under study. Electron withdrawing carbonyl group present at the nitrogen of the ring helps in drifting the electrons of sulphur towards the carbon of carbonyl group thus causing bathochromic shift. The wide band around at 310 nm in all these derivatives is possibly due to hypsochromic shift of the

Table I. UV Spectra of 10-N-acylamino phenothiazines

Compound	In water		In ethanol	
	λ_{max} nm	ϵ_{max}	λ_{max} nm	ϵ_{max}
2-Methoxy-phenothiazine	255	00893	250 320	01881 00617
A	237 250 265	10500 09285 09050	246 260 311	09597 10284 03293
B	236 259	08950 09475	240 255 312	09803 09262 02113
C	234 255	10825 10850	238 242 260 315	10918 10675 12104 03254
D	236 260	13500 09900	244 265 319	11179 10842 00617
E	238 265	17165 11267	234 242 265 315	07634 09972 11500 02000
F	233 260	13872 10636	236 242 260 312	08961 09275 09303 02425
G	232 267	15953 10034	242 255 318	13584 16495 05793
H	235 260	15244 11951	236 240 265 302	09099 10778 09671 02676
I	236 260	12561 09915	234 240 255 301	07877 08394 06903 01794

320 nm band. The band around 265 nm is shifted towards shorter wavelength region in the U.V. spectra of B, G and I due to the methyl group side chain near the carbonyl group (due to steric effect).

Infrared spectra

Although few references^{3,6,8} dealing with the infrared spectra of phenothiazines are available, the correlation of substituents with phenothiazine parent nucleus has not been done. Here an attempt has been made to show this correlation regarding the spectra of compounds under study. The I.R. spectral results of these compounds are listed in table 2. These compounds showed not only a characteristic but overall a unique absorption pattern.

Normal peaks arising from -N-H stretching appeared at 3380-3400 cm^{-1} . In compounds A-C, this is due to -N-H stretching vibrations of the side chain amino group as the hydrogen at N-H of the ring is

TABLE 2. IR SPECTRA OF 10-N-ACYLAMINOPHENOTHIAZINES (cm^{-1})

Compd.											Other peaks	
A	3400	2825 2420	1700	1600 1575	1475 1384 1367	1324 1316	1268 1232 1210	1175 1120	1060 1025	1210, 876, 775	920, 860,	1086
B	3400	2840 2420	1700	1604 1592 1580	1495 1384 1368	1324 1316	1284 1232	1158 1120	1072 1024	1216, 856, 775	932, 816,	972
C	3380	2860 2700 2380	1700	1604 1560	1500 1384 1368	1325 1312	1268 1236	1175 1136	1068 1036	1216, 860, 816,	992, 836, 775	1300, 1100, 760, 750, 664, 640
D	3455	3385 2856 2350	1700	1652 1580	1415 1375 1367	1325 1310	1260 1200	1125 1100	1070 1040	1200, 932, 820,	980, 876, 770,	1300, 1292 975, 900, 760, 700
E	3386	2960 2840 2410	1700	1608 1580 1550	1486 1420 1384 1364	1320 1304	1284 1225	1175 1125	1064 1025	1225, 964, 916, 864, 836, 816, 775	1116, 904, 860, 780, 750	
F	3400	2856 2350	1688	1604 1568	1460 1380 1360	1385 1285	1260 1220	1184 1116	1072 1050	985, 932, 864, 840, 816, 775	968, 900, 800, 865	
G	3400	2860 2670 2430	1690	1600 1584	1450 1384 1372	1272	1240 1224	1168 1124	1048 1032	1224, 992, 884, 775, 730	—	
H	3400	2850 2400	1684	1600 1584	1445 1384	1275	1235 1200	1150 1140	1070 1055	1200, 960, 916, 850, 808, 770	890, 664, 636	
I	3400	2856 2430	1684	1600 1560	1400 1384	131	1275 1235	1150 1145	1070 1030	1210, 930, 916, 850, 800	1050, 770	

substituted in these compounds^{8,9,10}. These peaks may either be due to enolic hydroxyl group¹¹ arising due to keto-enol tautomerism or due to protonation of nitrogen. This fact is ascertained by locking over the I. R. spectra of compounds D-I. These compounds though without -NH group, still showed band around 3400 cm^{-1} . This band in case of compounds H and I may be assigned due to the alcoholic -OH group (O-H stretching vibrations). It may be due to associated -OH group because free O-H stretching vibrations are shown at 3640 cm^{-1} . A band in the region of 3386-3455 cm^{-1} shown by compounds D-G is indicative of enolic group or protonated nitrogen as these compounds do not have N-H group of secondary amines or -OH (alcoholic) groups. This band may also be present in the I.R. spectra of rest of the compounds overlapped with N-H stretching bands.

All these compounds showed a broad band at 2825-2860 cm^{-1} with or without a hump at 2700 cm^{-1} and an additional peak between 2350-2430 cm^{-1} . Both these peaks may be due to secondary or tertiary amino salt¹⁰. The peak at 2825-2860 cm^{-1} may also be due to O-CH₃ or N-CH₃ (CH₃ symmetrical vibrations). The peaks in the region of 1030 to 1072 cm^{-1} and 1100 to 1140 cm^{-1} indicate the >C-O stretching due to primary to tertiary alcoholic group. This also supports the presence of an enolic group.

A strong peak in the region of 1230-1284 cm^{-1} may be assigned due to aryl methoxyl group.

These compounds also showed the usual characteristic peaks of phenothiazines, for example, peaks in the region of 1316-1360 cm^{-1} due to C-N stretching vibrations, two peaks in the region of 1560-1604 cm^{-1} due to aromatic ring system and four peaks in the region of 750-920 cm^{-1} due to 2-substituted phenothiazines (C-H out of plane deformations)^{3,6}. The peak due to enolic group in the region of 1560-1600 cm^{-1} must have been overlapped by peaks of aromatic -C=C- stretching vibrations.

A strong band at 700 cm^{-1} in the I.R. spectrum of the compound D is due to C-Cl stretching vibrations.

The compounds A to C have exhibited a strong band at 1260-1285 cm^{-1} and at 1200-1232 cm^{-1} . These peaks may be assigned to the skeletal vibrations of -C(CH₃)₃ groups. It is surprising to note that other compounds though without -C(CH₃)₃ group, also exhibited peaks in this region. These peaks may be due to either C-N twisting vibrations or O-CH₃ group present in all the compounds. The most characteristic peaks shown by the compounds under study appeared at 1684-1700 cm^{-1} and at 1460-1500 cm^{-1} . Both of these peaks are assigned to carbonyl group. The former peak due to >C=O stretching of tertiary amide group (where nitrogen is a part of heterocyclic ring), while the latter peak is due to

-CH₂-C = O group. It is interesting to note that in compounds H and I these peaks due to carbonyl group appeared at lower region 1680-1684 cm⁻¹ as compared with other compounds. It may be due to the primary alcoholic group present in these compounds which might have helped in the association of amide group.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Professor R. C. Kapoor, University of Jodhpur for encouragement and to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi for providing research fellowship to one of us (N.M.S.).

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